

Community activator toolkit

To support groups working for a safer, cleaner and fairer transport system

Activist's decision helper

Use our nifty decision tree to navigate this pack

ARE YOU A PART OF A CAMPAIGN GROUP OR ORGANISATION?

Foreword

What do you love about transport and mobility where you live? What do you hate?

We all have an opinion about how we get about our cities and towns. From how much we love to cycle, to how much we loathe traffic jams and costly public transport. Now, what if you could do something about this, and actually turn words into action?

WeCount was set up to help do just that. By providing citizens with traffic counting devices, that measured cars, large vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists, as well as the speed of cars, they were able to take ownership of the production of data where they lived. Working together with others on their street and their neighbourhood, citizens have been supported to analyse the data and take action appropriate to their context.

Among the actions they took were to: install sensors in community settings and schools for further engagement; lobby the government, businesses or the police; apply for funding; and raise awareness among their community. New speed cameras have been installed, the sensor has been hacked to work outside, and almost half of all participating citizens plan to continue working with the data post-WeCount.

This toolkit is for all the citizens who have so far taken part in WeCount, and for all those wanting to 'carry the baton' and make use of data on WeCount's data platform for future use. You do not need a traffic sensor to act, however we offer guidance on what to buy or alternatives you can use, should you wish to collect primary data.

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Define your identity

We each play a different role in activism, be that in caring for the activists, protesting on the streets, researching the latest evidence, creating alternatives to the capitalist model, making connections or communicating the message. No one fits neatly into one category, or can always be active, however knowing which type of role you play (or would like to play) is key to ensure you say yes to what you enjoy - and say no to the things you don't.

Circle the box that best describes your role, or take The Story of Stuff Project's quiz to find out:

<https://action.storyofstuff.org/survey/change-maker-quiz/>

THE STORY OF
STUFF

Define your purpose

Your purpose is your mission statement. It defines how you see yourself in the world and the contribution you are making/hope to make. Think through these questions and then write your statement.

What are your positive attributes - your skills and traits that make you, you? Look around you and if in doubt, ask others.

What would you like to learn that will bring more joy to your life? What change would you like to see in your community, or in the world? How could you use your voice, skills, or expertise to help other people?

Reflect on these questions and then use the space opposite to flesh out your statement. You could write ideas on post-its first, if it is helpful.

My mission statement

Setting up a campaign group

More often than not there will already be a campaign working to solve your issue, so begin by looking at what is already going on in your area. Is there a local health or environmental action group, or a local chapter of a national organisation (like Friends of the Earth or Extinction Rebellion) you could join? Attend one of their meetings and see if what they do aligns with your agenda. If you feel you need to set up your own campaign then proceed as follows:

Form a group

Who else do you know who shares your concerns? Call upon neighbours, colleagues, friends or parents - explain your story and ask if they would like to be part of tackling the issue. Decisions are best made in small groups so bare this in mind when establishing yours.

Agree a collective vision

What do you want your city to look like in 2050? How will people navigate the city? What will transport infrastructure look like? How will people behave? Spend time developing a collective vision early on. Your ideas may be different to others - to increase the chances of group cohesion, agree on a vision that works for everyone.

Decide upon roles

What skills and passions do people bring? How much time do they have? When and where can people meet? Who will chair meetings and how will decisions be taken? Avoid hierarchies and agree on roles. Put in place a method for reviewing roles and group dynamic so no one person dominates or is taking on too much. Agree on a code of conduct to hold people to account.

Setting up a campaign group

Create a plan of action

Define the problem, the solution and the steps needed to get there. Take time to craft your story and set SMART objectives - specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and, timely. Divide up tasks and decide among the group who will take on each task. Use project management tools like Slack to communicate remotely and support one another to get task done. It is important to have some structure among the fluidity to ensure you remain organised and focussed.

Consult those most interested and partner with those with most influence

Map stakeholders (see page 8) - people in positions of power (e.g. institutions, councils, businesses, community organisations and leaders) and people most interested in the issue. This allows you to understand who needs to be engaged and when during your campaign.

Take time to check in and reflect

Throughout your campaign there will be highs and lows, wins and losses. Take time to honour each member of the group, regularly asking them how they are feeling and doing. Value each contribution equally and make caring for yourself and the group a top priority! Reflect on your practices and be willing to adapt as new things come to light. Stay curious.

Before you begin to engage the public, first take time to reflect on the groups values (p9) and their communication styles (p10), and how this translates to your stakeholders. Overlooking these is a key reason why groups fall apart.

Stakeholder mapping template

Use this template to map your stakeholders.

Potential influence

Potential interest

How campaigns become echo chambers

Campaigns that focus solely on the 'big picture', without concrete actions that relate to people's everyday lives, tend to attract people with high levels of 'self-agency' (the belief that you can change the world as opposed to it limiting or changing you). Even though fewer than 10% of the UK population would see themselves as agents of change, up to 90% of some campaign NGOs staff fall into this category, while about 60% of their supporters do.

Environmental and communications consultant, Chris Rose, says these people are 'transcenders', a segment of society that fall within the Pioneer category of the pie chart opposite. Prospectors, meanwhile, are more timid when it comes to self-agency, but can be shown the way. Settlers are less likely to change, and need authorities to tell them what to do. These groups are fluid and change over space (e.g., city v. rural) and time (e.g., young v. old).

Three Maslow Groups of unmet needs and behaviours

Outer directed. Need for success and esteem of other before self-esteem. Acquire and display symbols of success

Change? *Maybe, if you can show me it works.*
Questions? *What's the right answer?*
Driver of change: dreams, possibility

Sustenance driven. Need for security, safety, belonging. Like to stay local and avoid risk.

Change? *No thanks, you lead*
Questions? *I'd rather not here than*
Driver of change: clarity, simplicity

Innder director. Need to connect actions with values, explore ideas and experiment. Network, innovate, ethically and interest driven.

Change? *Of course - and I have my own ideas.*
Questions? *But are you asking the right ones (there are no 'right answers')*
Driver of change: vision

To find out more: bit.ly/maslowgrps

Task: Different people do the same thing for different reasons

What Maslow Group do the following statements relate to?:

A. We just bought solar panels for our house. We will be able to save money and feel safer in the knowledge that we are in control of our own energy production

.....

B. Our neighbours installed panels on their roof and we thought it silly not to do the same! We live on the other side of the road so we are not south facing, but we will get some sunlight at least.

.....

C. I am concerned about the state of the planet and we all have to do our bit to make a difference. That is why I decided to get solar panels.

.....

Answers: a) settlers; b) prospectors; c) pioneers

The action pyramid of polarisation

Because our intuitions come first and reasoning second, it is what we do that changes what we believe, not the other way around. This explains why two people, best friends in childhood, become estranged as adults. One moved away to university and the other remained in their village. Each decision they made took them further away from their starting point, with things in common, to a situation where they have nothing to say.

The **media** we read reinforces our potential for action, with research finding the Guardian is the UK outlet with the most coverage of solutions to climate change, while the Daily Mail is the outlet with the most references to it as a crisis, but offers no solutions. If we lack **role models** that show people like us can make a change, we are also less likely to act.

What works at engaging people?

Learning from personal experience

- Sensory experiences (visual, tactile, auditory, see p14)
- Mental experiences (self-reflection, "seeing yourself see")
- Use spatial and temporal frames that the human mind can manage
- Translate to values and perspectives that are familiar to certain groups

Social learning

- Learning directly from someone's experience
- Seeing someone else learn from experience
- Importance of friendliness, trust, respect for values for social learning to take place

Effective science communication

- Find your warm, authentic voice
- Tell personal stories: facts work in stories (explaining facts is not enough to explain your intuitive understanding)
- Explain your motivations and what your research means to you - allow your audience to empathise with the emotional journey of your research
- Recognise you may misunderstand the motivations of those who criticise. Your audience may disagree with you because of what they *know* and what they *value*. Use active listening (p13) to overcome this and find common ground
- Be kind but do not tolerate abuse
- Humour and play are often good; anger, mocking and smugness are not

For more tips, see event guide (p22)

Active listening

Listening is a critical skill for any job and impacts on the quality of our relationships with others. Yet research suggests that on average we remember 25-50% of what we hear. We can all improve this skill through "active listening" - making a conscious effort to hear the words others say, and to clarify any questions you have so you understand the complete message.

Try this exercise with a friend, or in your next meeting. Pay close attention to what the person says, repeating the words in your head if helpful, and then repeat back the message to them in the form of a question to see if you understood.

'Listen' to their body language and make gestures (e.g. nod) to show you are listening.

It can help to keep an open and receptive posture and allow the person time to fully express themselves. Embrace the silences and avoid jumping in when they still have something to say. Refrain from judgement, instead responding with follow-up questions. "That's interesting, why do you think that is?" Empathise: "That sounds difficult. How did you overcome that?"

Reflections from the exercise

Sensing the environment

When we arrive at a new place we often take our time getting familiar with it. What does the place remind us of? Where are the amenities? In time, we begin to notice the details, like where the best places are to eat ice cream, what streets to avoid at night, the fastest routes into town. The more we pay attention to something, the more we begin to notice the detail.

Scientists engage their senses to systematically understand the natural world. They turn their attention to a specific issue and methodically study the behaviour. Once there is sufficient evidence, they then take action. We can do the same with traffic and transport issues. By employing some tried and tested scientific methods, we can start to identify where issues arise and take action with the data we generate. If we take people on this journey, who may not otherwise be interested in these issues, they too may become champions of the cause.

Today, we can manually sense the environment, by documenting smells, noises, the number of things, etc., or use technology, such as speed cameras, traffic sensors and air quality sensors. The benefit of digital technology is that they can gather much more data in a shorter period of time. Ideally we would use both, but if that is not possible then one method will do! Read on for inspiration on what tools you can use.

Sensing the environment

Pre-existing data

A lot of local councils these days will be collecting data on traffic and air quality. They may even consult people on proposed developments or conduct surveys on citizens views about say perceptions of road safety. Perform some desk research first to see what is out there, and what will help you answer your research question. Most WeCount citizens have been gathering data on traffic types, volumes and car speeds for over one year, providing rich data if you happen to live in one of the case study cities. Explore [Telraam.net/en](https://www.telraam.net/en) to see if you are in luck.

Technology-mediated

You can buy the components for a Telraam for around £80. You can also buy **add ons** for Raspberry Pi's to monitor noise and pollutions. These add ons are great education tools, however their accuracy is questionable. Telraam is up to 90% accurate, providing reliable data that can be taken seriously by decision makers. Other sensors (e.g. for air pollution) are available, however they are costly. Funds are available though, such as through the National Lottery's **Community Fund**. If you are keen to buy the tech, then explore options for financial support. And make sure you or someone you know is tech-savvy! We have provided instructions on how to set up Telraam and answers to common questions on the [Telraam website](https://www.telraam.net/en).

Manual counts

Manual counts are an important step in the scientific process to ensure the technology accurately reflects reality. It is also useful when technology is unavailable or not as good as our own senses. Our sense of smell for example, cannot be replicated by a machine. The [urban smell map](#) is a great tool if this is what you want to investigate.

Data collection

How long will you be collecting data for? On what times of day/days of the week? And why?

Think through your data collection strategy. Make it easy for yourself by using pre-existing data where possible, and complimenting with primary data collection when necessary. Adding local voices, either from surveys or focus groups can be of particular benefit (see page 20).

To get a detailed picture of changes to traffic and transport over time, it is important to document changes caused by weather, roadworks and other variables. For instance, you may find more cyclists and fewer cars on sunny days. While roadworks may reduce traffic volumes on the effected road but push it onto neighbouring streets.

Data analysis

What themes are emerging from the data?
Does the evidence support your hypothesis?

Create graphs and tables to present your data in an engaging way. Don't forget to include labels and keys - anyone that sees this information should be able to understand what it means with minimal effort. Combine quantitative data with qualitative data from any surveys you have and create a communication fit for your purposes. Tell the story of your data within the context of the big picture problem (e.g., climate change), your city (e.g., traffic and air pollution) and your community (e.g., concerns, 'rat run', etc). Write the text to inform or influence your intended audience. Write persuasively, in a style that would appeal to your readers values.

Prototyping solutions

The emerging data can also be used to prototype solutions to the problem. Take speeding cars. You could prototype a digital speed sign and test out how effective different messages were at slowing down cars. Or you could create a visual cue in the environment, such as pictures of children crossing or old people crossing. Of course, these are quite conventional methods, but you can get creative with your ideas. Be bold and brainstorm ideas, big and small, on post-its. Then, as a group, figure out which is the most important and the most feasible by placing on the graph provided.

Test out the winning solution, e.g. by sketching out designs and asking the opinion of neighbours/those impacted by the proposed idea. Refine as necessary.

Reaching your audience

There are three ways to reach your audience. Where possible, try all three methods, and try several times in different locations and/or times to reach as diverse a population as possible.

Reach Out

Speak with target organisations and asked to be invited in to speak with your target audience. Manage expectations and emphasise the mutual benefits of working together. If possible, seek out local champions who can promote your cause more widely among their peers.

Pop up

Create stalls at specific events/at certain locations with high footfall. Useful for speaking with the general public. To stand out, you will need to devise a game or activity that hooks people in and conveys your message in just a few minutes. Make your stall bright and welcoming and be prepared to answer questions.

Invite in

Invite to standalone events to raise awareness of cause. A word of caution: this takes a lot of effort and may not result in large numbers unless your issue is particularly topical or your organisation is well-established. Inviting well-known speakers and promoting through respected channels (e.g. local media) can increase likelihood of a large turnout.

Amplifying marginalised voices

The most vulnerable members of society are impacted the most by development, yet they often have the least say in decision-making processes.

Seek out marginalised peoples in your campaigns to diversify perspectives on the issue. Go door-to-door or connect with relevant community organisations and spaces, and use creative ways to amplify their voice. In addition to traditional quotes from surveys, you could **film** them saying something about the issue, how it impacts their daily life and what they want to see changed, ask them to use the **camera** on their phone to capture their lived experience or ask them to draw their hopes and concerns directly onto a **map of their area**, with symbols and a key.

Influencing stakeholders

Now that you have your data and a possible solution that works for your community, put forward your argument to decision makers. This could be funding bodies, the policy, local councillors, or businesses. Figure out who it is you need to influence and then tailor your approach accordingly.

Find a way to meet them in person, in addition to sharing the evidence and ideas via email. Remember to keep your cool and present the facts. Speak from the heart but emphasise why things need to change, your results (hard evidence) and the costs and benefits your proposal will bring. You may not succeed first time. Be open to feedback and do not let setbacks stop you. If needed, try again with another person/organisation, and learn from each encounter.

For additional support on how to fundraise, write press releases and working with elected representatives, see: <https://campaigning.friendsoftheearth.uk/general-resources>

Event guide

To decide which events you would like to attend, you first need to think about **WHY** you are undertaking public engagement. Once you have a list of your aims and objectives, you should then know more about **WHO** you need to engage with. After that, you can then decide **HOW** you can interest and entertain audiences. This is called strategic communication, and it is essential to understand and evaluate whether you fulfill your aims.

What is your big idea?

In order to interact with audiences, you first need to know what you are going to say. This means knowing the 'big picture' of your story, including why the issues matter, the data to support your claims, and what you are doing about the problem. If in doubt, ask yourself (or someone else) "why should anyone care"? It's your job to make the topic relevant to people. This means thinking about what people are interested in, what they know about, what they are worried about, and connecting the issues to their lives.

Who are you talking to?

Picture your audience. Practice giving simple explanations, out loud, in advance. Ideally, test your ideas on people who aren't experts – maybe your children, your grandmother, or friends. At events it is usually best to start with the most simple answer you can manage, then judge from the person's reaction how much detail they might want. Before an event ask: What are the specific interests or needs of your potential audience? How does this work connect to everyday experiences and concerns? Are there popular television programmes or famous people that are influential in this area? Has there been a big news story recently that could make the topic relevant? During an event test your assumptions and different messages/ideas; use the information participants give you to make examples and explanations more relevant.

Event guide

How will you capture their attention?

What will make your event or stall stand out among the crowd? How will you market the event and what will people get in return? For the stall or space itself, how will you entice people in? Will there be food, games or activities? Tie interactivity to your topic and use this to raise awareness or encourage people to join your cause. Having the presence of role models or local champions can be especially useful in terms of gaining local support.

Evaluating your activities

Evaluation can show impact, show what worked and what didn't, can also help you secure funding; and it is the only way to discover if you have achieved your strategic communication aims. Determine your measurable outcomes and then evaluate accordingly, e.g. with 'pledge boards', smiley faces, snapshot interviews, feedback boxes or something that doesn't feel like evaluation for participants, along with personal reflections.

Event best practice

- Attend pre-existing events in a variety of locations
- Connect your topic to contexts people understand, using big ideas rather than too many details
- Use everyday language - avoid jargon/technical terms
- Use hands-on activities to engage people in conversation
- Ensure there are enough staff to talk to the visitors
- Signpost people if you don't know the answer/take down email addresses and follow up
- Provide positive solutions and take away materials

Story Arc Design Template

Drawing from design thinking, this template allows you to quickly jot down your ideas, seek feedback and keep refining till your idea is workable. Spend just 5 minutes drafting the story for your event, then ask for feedback from someone you hope to engage/an engagement practitioner.

	Draft 1	Feedback	Draft 2
THE WHY Desired outcome at the end of the session			
Narrative arc What is the beginning, middle and end			
Timings No. of activities; length of activities; breaks/reflections; intro/conclusion			
Materials What you need to run the session?			
Data capture What will you capture, and how?			

Social media guide

Social media can be an effective way of reaching a large audience, however it takes time to build a fan base.

Do your research

Look at what is already out there so a) you don't 'reinvent the wheel' and b) you can learn from others. Find out what relevant events or campaigns are coming up and plan your activities around these key moments. Use the hashtag of big events/ campaigns to reach more people. Things to bear in mind: around 70% of users in Europe use Facebook, 10% use Twitter, 8% use Instagram and less than 2% use YouTube. However, this differs by age group and by country. Each platform serves a different role. YouTube is for entertainment, Instagram for brand discovery and inspiration, Facebook for messenger and events, and Twitter for news, trends and information.

Decide how much time you have

If you have less than one hour per week to commit then consider using just one or two channels and be selective with what you choose to share, or consider partnering with an existing platform and share your messages through their channels. If you have more time, read on!

Develop your strategy

Why use social media? What do you want to say? To whom? When? And how? Plan and seek advice. Knowing your audience is key, especially as not everyone uses social media.

Social media guide

Grow your brand

Assuming you have decided on your key message(s), target audience, platform(s) and time commitment, you can now begin to grow your brand.

Social media check list:

- Set up platform(s): think of a unique and attractive name that people will want to follow if you don't already have one
- Create branding (e.g. logos, social media templates, a colour scheme, etc) using free tools like Canva.com
- Reach out, follow and interact with influencers (big names in the field of health, cities, air quality, climate change, etc)
- Join an existing campaign and use their available marketing material, or create your own
- Keep posts light, informative and on occasion interactive (e.g. polls), with a clear message and call to action
- Be interactive and authentic with your audience
- Avoid politics, derogatory or offensive language/imagery, facts without references and content that is irrelevant/distracts from your message

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